

ParAqua COST Action CA20125 Data Management Plan

Version 1

Description

The main aims of the COST Action CA20125 Applications For Zoosporic Parasites In Aquatic Systems, in short ParAqua, are to organize and coordinate an innovative and dynamic Network, connecting academia, industries and water management authorities to advance and apply knowledge and expertise on zoosporic parasites (i.e. aquatic fungi and fungi-like microorganisms) and the relation with their hosts in natural ecosystems and industrial algal biotech production.

Among the ParAqua objectives, specific task of WG1 and WG2 is to compile and integrate a database on zoosporic parasites across Europe and inventorise parasite effects on algal hosts in algal biotech and natural systems.

The purpose of this Data Management Plan is the description of how data is handled in the ParAqua Action in order to enable the sharing and reutilization of the data gathered during the Action lifetime, promoting an open and FAIR Research Data Management. For sake of clarity and to streamline the process of data mobilisation, we describe the data into four datasets type: i) "occurrences" dataset, which will contain data of presence/absence of parasites; ii) "traits" dataset, for the description of all the morpho-functional traits; iii) "environmental variables" dataset, for the accessories environmental measurements; iiiii) "literature data", which comprises mainly the data that are collected in literature to build the paper on occurrences and sequences of alga parasite foreseen in ParAqua WG1.

LifeWatch Italy, the national node of the eScience European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research LifeWatch ERIC, will collaborate by providing the IT infrastructure, tools, services and skills for sharing the acquired knowledge and assure the long-term sustainability of the data managed within ParAqua.

This Data Management Plan is intended as a live document, and will be regularly updated whenever needed.

This publication is based upon work from COST Action 20125 - Applications for zoosporic parasites in aquatic systems (ParAqua), supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology) is a funding agency for research and innovation networks. Our Actions help connect research initiatives across Europe and enable scientists to grow their ideas by sharing them with their peers. This boosts their research, career and innovation.

www.cost.eu

www.paraqua-cost.eu

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Researchers

Slawek Cerbin (orcid:0000-0002-2800-0390), Hans-Peter Grossart (orcid:0000-0002-9141-0325), Laura Garzoli (orcid:0000-0003-1353-9120), Ilaria Rosati (orcid:0000-0003-3422-7230), Elzbieta Wilk-Wozniak (orcid:0000-0002-4929-6733), Tena Radočaj (orcid:0000-0003-1755-9823), Serena Rasconi (orcid:0000-0001-6667-8904), Albert Reñé (orcid:0000-0002-0488-3539), Jovica Leshoski (orcid:0000-0002-0915-7173), Andrea Tarallo (orcid:0000-0002-2749-8588), Dijana Blazhekovikj - Dimovska (orcid:0000-0001-5912-9093)

Organizations

Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Polish Academy of Sciences, Institute of Nature Conservation, Université Savoie Mont Blanc, National Research Council of Italy (CNR), UNIVERSITY ST KLIMENT OHRIDSKI BITOLA, Institut de Ciències del Mar, Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement (INRAE), Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Agriculture

Datasets

Title: Environmental descriptors

Template: Horizon Europe

This dataset contains information on environmental descriptors related to occurrences and traits of zoosporic parasites.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

We are re-using pre-existing data, mainly produced by members and already published. In the case of already published data, we will consider copyrights and permissions, properly citing the original source or publication.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

Comma Separated Values

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Average size of the collected dataset will be about 50 to 100 KB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To make informed decisions

- To develop a product
- To combine with other data

The first objective is to make available data on environmental drivers of algal parasites to the large community of scientists and innovators. This will be done by mobilising the data that were collected in previous projects in a harmonised way to a database. The database is a deliverable of the project ParAqua (CA20125). It will provide a single entry point for data on zoosporic parasites, and a tool for environmental descriptors associated to the parasites occurrence and outbreaks in nature or industrial settings.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data produced by ParAqua members for research/ investigation purposes. ParAqua members will contribute with data coming from different projects and respective countries on infections in industrial (algal biotech) and natural systems and harmonised according to the common dataset template.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Economy
- Industry

The datasets will be made available through a public database that will collect and expose information on zoosporic parasites of algae and can be used in research (e.g. meta-analyses, information on biology and ecology of species, food web functioning, ecosystem restoration and management). It can also be used by industries such as algae farms to manage outbreaks of parasites in cultures.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

Handle

All the datasets that will be uploaded on the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal will be assigned a handle. Datasets which will be provided with rich metadata and will be openly accessible will receive a DOI.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

All the datasets that will be uploaded on the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal will be described by metadata based on a derivation of EML 2.2.0 schema. The database will be described by metadata as well.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Structural
- Reference

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

- a. <https://dwc.tdwg.org/list/>
- b. <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue

- Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

LifeWatch Italy Data Portal

<https://dataportal.lifewatchitaly.eu/data>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Datasets will be long-term stored on the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal and made accessible through a dedicated web interface that will be maintained by the LifeWatch Italy (CNR-IRET Lecce) and LifeWatch ERIC Service Centre.

Datasets will be freely accessible and downloadable without any kind of authorization required.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

At the moment, due to project contract bindings, the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal will be maintained for at least ten years. As national node of an European Research Infrastructure Consortium, the lifetime is virtually forever.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata will explicitly include the PID of the datasets.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Metadata will be stored on the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal and to the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue. LifeWatch ERIC lifetime is virtually forever.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Darwin Core

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

EML (Ecological Metadata Language)

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The terminology used is described by their resolvable URI. Metadata will contain PIDs to any other external existing reference to the specific dataset.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Data cleaning
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

24000

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

Direct cost

Cost is calculated from 6 person/month plus 25% of overheads.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure
- Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Andrea Tarallo (orcid:0000-0002-2749-8588)

ParAqua WG1 co-leader, leader of the activity of data mobilisation within ParAqua

b. Ilaria Rosati (orcid:0000-0003-3422-7230)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

LifeWatch Italy Data Manager

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

unknown

Ethical: NO, Legal: YES - some of the data may need consent from copyright owners (e.g. someone keeps the data on his/her own computer without making it public after publication).

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [Occurrences](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

The purpose is to collect information from ParAqua members about occurrence of zoosporic parasites in their research projects, in algal biotech and natural ecosystems across Europe, thus benefitting from the expertise present in the network. From this, we will derive parasite-control strategies that can secure sustainable algal biomass production by supporting monitoring and enhance a fundamental understanding of the role of zoosporic parasites in natural and algal biotech systems.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

We are mostly re-using pre-existing data, mainly already published. Some new data may be generated during the project. In case of already published data, we will include the reference to the publication. The dataset will be also published as a data paper.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Mostly primary observational and experimental data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Comma Separated Values

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Average size of the collected dataset will be about 50 to 100 KB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To combine with other data

The first objective is to make available data on occurrences of algal parasites to the large community of scientists and innovators. This will be done by mobilising the data that were collected in previous projects in a harmonised way to a database. The database is a deliverable of the project ParAqua (CA20125). It will provide a single entry point for data on zoosporic parasites, and a tool for the early detection of parasites in nature or industrial settings.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data produced by ParAqua members for research/ investigation purposes, mostly from previous projects (e.g. PARAL Spanish Project; COPAS Spanish Project; SMART Spanish Project, Italian aquaculture monitoring programmes, ECOTREAT, Research projects funded by the Ministry of Environment and Ministry of Education and Science of R. Macedonia, French Ministry of Higher Education and Research, DFG-projects, other EU projects such as Biodiversa, and other initiatives at national and European level).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

Handle

All the datasets that will be uploaded on the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal will be assigned a handle. Datasets which will be provided with rich metadata and will be openly accessible will receive a DOI.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

All the datasets that will be uploaded on the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal will be described by metadata based on a derivation of EML 2.2.0 schema. The database will be described by metadata as well.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Structural
- Reference

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <https://dwc.tdwg.org/list/>

b. <https://ecoportal.lifewatch.eu/ontologies/PHYTOTRAITS>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

The metadata file will be available on the LifeWatch ERIC metadata catalogue, and to the LifeWatch Italy metadata catalogue that will be soon released.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

LifeWatch Italy Data Portal

<https://dataportal.lifewatchitaly.eu/data>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Datasets will be long-term stored on the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal and made accessible through a dedicated web interface that will be maintained by the LifeWatch Italy (CNR-IRET Lecce) and LifeWatch ERIC Service Centre.

Datasets will be freely accessible and downloadable without any kind of authorization required.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

At the moment, due to project contract bindings, the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal will be maintained for at least ten years. As national node of an European Research Infrastructure Consortium, the lifetime is virtually forever.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata will explicitly include the PID of the datasets.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Metadata will be stored on the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal and to the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue. LifeWatch ERIC lifetime is virtually forever.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Darwin Core, PhytoTraits

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

<https://ecoportal.lifewatch.eu/ontologies/PHYTOTRAITS>

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

EML (Ecological Metadata Language)

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The terminology used is described by their resolvable URI. Metadata will contain PIDs to any other external existing reference to the specific dataset.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Data cleaning
- Variable definitions

- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

24000,00

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Direct cost

Cost is calculated from 6 person/month plus 25% of overheads.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure
- Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Andrea Tarallo (orcid:0000-0002-2749-8588)

ParAqua WG1 co-leader, leader of the activity of data mobilisation within ParAqua

b. Ilaria Rosati (orcid:0000-0003-3422-7230)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

LifeWatch Italy Data Manager

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Traits

Template: Horizon Europe

The purpose of this dataset is to collect and describe the data management actions related to the collection of information on parasites' traits and make it available on an interactive and user-friendly platform.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

We are re-using pre-existing data, mainly already published. In case of already published data, we will include the reference to the publication. The dataset will be also published as a data paper.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Mostly Secondary data (cleaned, checked and at least undergone preliminary analyses). Data will be mainly observational (captured *in situ*) and experimental (under controlled conditions).

1.1.5 What is its format?

Comma Separated Values

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Average size of the collected dataset will be about 50 to 100 KB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To combine with other data

The first objective is to make available data on traits of algal parasites to the large community of scientists and innovators. This will be done by mobilising the data that were collected in previous projects in a harmonised way to a database. The database is a deliverable of the project ParAqua (CA20125). It will provide a single entry point for data on zoosporic parasites, and a tool for the traits characterisation of parasites in nature and industrial settings.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data produced by ParAqua members for research/ investigation purposes. ParAqua members will contribute with data coming from different projects and respective countries on infections in industrial (algal biotech) and natural systems and harmonised according the common dataset template.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

As for industry example, it will be very useful for aquaculture growers of algae, for easy recognition and characterization of parasites occurring in the aquaculture. Researchers can use the database to create projects and PhD theses in the field of zoosporic parasites.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

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3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Structural
- Reference

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

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3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <https://dwc.tdwg.org/list/>

b. <https://ecoportal.lifewatch.eu/ontologies/PHYTOTRAITS>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

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3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

LifeWatch Italy Data Portal

<https://dataportal.lifewatchitaly.eu/data>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Datasets will be long-term stored on the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal and made accessible through a dedicated web interface that will be maintained by the LifeWatch Italy (CNR-IRET Lecce) and LifeWatch ERIC Service Centre.

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3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

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3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Metadata will be stored on the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal and to the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue. LifeWatch ERIC lifetime is virtually forever.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Darwin Core, PhytoTraits

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

<https://ecoportal.lifewatch.eu/ontologies/PHYTOTRAITS>

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

EML (Ecological Metadata Language)

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The terminology used is described by their resolvable URI. Metadata will contain PIDs to any other external existing reference to the specific dataset.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Data cleaning
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

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Euro

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Direct cost

Cost is calculated from 6 person/month plus 25% of overheads.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
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- Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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ParAqua WG1 co-leader, leader of the activity of data mobilisation within ParAqua

b. Ilaria Rosati (orcid:0000-0003-3422-7230)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

LifeWatch Italy Data Manager

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

unknown

Most likely not - some geolocalised data (lakes, reservoirs, etc...). Maybe some data related to industrial facilities is easily identifiable.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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